

ROLE OF MANGANESE IN THE BIOLOGICAL SYNTHESIS OF ASCORBIC ACID. THE SYNTHESIS OF INDO-PHENOL REDUCING SUBSTANCES BY GUINEA-PIG LIVER *IN VITRO* AND *IN VIVO*.

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The ability of normal guinea-pig liver to synthesise indophenol-reducing substances *in vitro* and *in vivo* in presence of adequate concentrations of manganese has been demonstrated. A hypothesis that the inability of the guinea-pig and the primates to synthesise ascorbic acid within the body is due to insufficiency of manganese, which acts in the capacity of a co-enzyme in the tissues, has been advanced. The probability of synthesis of ascorbic acid in human being under certain suitable (generally acid) conditions has been discussed.

Guha and Ghosh (*Nature*, 1934, **134**, 739) reported that rat-liver could synthesise ascorbic acid from mannose *in vitro* and *in vivo*. They also reported (*Nature*, 1935, **135**, 234) that normal or scorbutic guinea-pig tissue could not apparently synthesise ascorbic acid from mannose but that embryonic guinea-pig tissue and the ovarian tissue of the pregnant guinea-pig could synthesise ascorbic acid from mannose. They also claimed that only mannose can act as a precursor and although glucose gave some positive results *in vivo* experiments, they opined that the sugar must pass through a mannose-like configuration before it is synthesised into ascorbic acid. The claim of Guha and Ghosh (*loc. cit.*) regarding the synthesis of ascorbic acid from mannose by rat-liver has been challenged by others (Euler, Gartz and Malmberg, *Biochem. Z.*, 1935, **282**, 399; Hawthorne and Harrison, *Biochem. J.*, 1937, **31**, 1061; Klodt, *Arch. Exp. Path. Pharmacol.*, 1938, **189**, 157; Mentzer and Urbain, *Compt. rend. Soc. Biol.*, 1938, **128**, 270). Sztareczy (*Biochem. Z.*, 1938, **298**, 369) concludes that *l*-sorbose and to a less extent mannose can act as ascorbic acid precursors in the rat-intestine (*cf.* also Lemos, *Compt. rend.*, 1939, **208**, 946).

The author (*Nature*, 1939, **143**, 881) has shown that manganese is a determining factor in the synthesis of ascorbic acid by rat-liver and has suggested an explanation of the inability of other investigators (Euler *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) to demonstrate the synthesis of ascorbic acid *in vitro* or *in vivo* by rat-liver. It has also been shown by the author that not only mannose but other sugars like galactose and glucose can also act as precursors. It has now been found that normal guinea-pig liver also can synthesise ascorbic acid from the sugar precursors *in vitro* and *in vivo* in presence of adequate concentrations of manganese.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Experiments in vitro.

To demonstrate the synthesis of ascorbic acid by normal guinea-pig liver *in vitro*, the experiments of Hawthorne and Harrison (*loc. cit.*) were repeated with guinea-pig liver and with the modification that the Ringer-Locke solution in which the minced liver was incubated for demonstrating the synthesis of ascorbic acid, contained various concentrations of manganese as manganese chloride. Mannose and galactose were employed as precursors. The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

In vitro.

M N i n	incubated-	Sugar.	Ascorbic acid content of liver after 3 hours' incubation (mg./g).	Remarks.
Ringer-Locke.	mixture.			
1. 0'10%	0'05%	Mannose	0'18	—
0'02	0'01	"	0'16	—
0'01	0'005	"	0'15	—
0'002	0'001	"	0'14	—
Nil	Nil	Nil	0'14	Control; with liver but no sugar.
2. 0'10	0'05	Mannose	0'18	—
0'02	0'01	"	0'16	—
0'01	0'005	"	0'15	—
0'002	0'0005	"	0'14	—
Nil	Nil	Nil	0'14	Control.
3. 0'10	0'05	Mannose	0'20	—
0'02	0'01	"	0'16	—
0'01	0'005	"	0'14	—
Nil	Nil	Nil	0'14	Control.
Fresh liver without incubation.			0'22	—
4. 0'10	0'05	Galactose	0'17	—
0'02	0'01	"	0'15	—
0'01	0'005	"	0'13	—
Nil	Nil	Nil	0'13	Control.
Fresh liver without incubation			0'22	—

The results obtained with the incubated tissues are comparable among themselves. Values obtained with the fresh tissue without incubation are naturally higher as incubation causes some loss of ascorbic acid due to oxidation.

Experiments in vivo.

Animals of the same litter and of the same sex were employed for these experiments. Depending upon the weight of the animals, 25 mg. or 40 mg. of mannose contained in 0.5 c.c. or 1 c.c. respectively of dilute manganese chloride solution were injected intraperitoneally. In the controls same volume of normal saline was similarly given. The animals were killed 8 hours or 5 hours after injection and the ascorbic acid content of the liver determined by the microchemical method with 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol. The titrations (as well as the *in vitro* titrations) were done under ice and were finished in equal time by timing with a stopwatch. In one case a very dilute solution of manganese only was injected. The results are given in Table II.

TABLE II.

In vivo.

Exp. (Intraperitoneally).	Mg. of ascorbic acid per g. of liver.	Remarks.
1. 25 Mg. of mannose in 0.5 c.c. of 0.05% Mn (as MnCl ₂).	0.30	Killed after 8 hrs.
0.5 c.c. normal saline (N.S.)	0.24	—
2. 25 Mg. of mannose in 0.5 c.c. of 0.04% Mn.	0.27	Killed after 5 hrs.
0.5 c.c. N.S.	0.21	—
3. 40 Mg. of galactose in 1 c.c. of 0.04% Mn.	0.25	"
40 Mg. of mannose in 1 c.c. of 0.02% Mn.	0.24	"
1 c.c. N.S.	0.21	—
4. 40 Mg. of mannose in 1 c.c. of 0.02% Mn.	0.24	"
1 c.c. N.S.	0.21	—
5. 0.5 C.c. of 0.001% Mn:	0.22	—
0.5 c.c. N.S.	0.22	—

DISCUSSION.

In this work we have proceeded with the assumption that under the conditions of our experiments, the indophenol titration would give the value for true ascorbic acid. The author does not, thereby, exclude the possible synthesis of non-specific indophenol-reducing substances. The investigation on this problem is proceeding and the synthesis of non-specific reducing substances, if any, will be the subject matter of a subsequent work to be taken in hand.

It will be seen that normal guinea-pig liver can synthesise appreciable

amounts of ascorbic acid (up to 0.06 mg. per g. of liver) *in vitro* as well as *in vivo*. Mannose and galactose can function as precursors. It is conceivable that other sugars may also play the role of precursors (*cf.* also Rudra, *loc. cit.*) In conjunction with the results obtained by the author and reported earlier (*Nature*, 1939, 143, 881; *Biochem. Z.*, 1939, 301, 268) it is now fairly convincingly proved that manganese is an important link in the mechanism by which the precursors (at least the sugar precursors) are converted into ascorbic acid, manganese acting as the co-enzyme to the dehydrogenase acting on the hexoses. It is interesting to note that Edlbacher and Baur (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1938, 254, 275) found that arginase acts in association with manganese and other metallic ions and they found that manganese is the co-enzyme of arginase and is present with a protein carrier. It would also appear that the enzyme or the enzymes (dehydrogenases) which transform the precursors into ascorbic acid, is present in the guinea pig tissue but its inability to synthesise ascorbic acid *in vivo* is due to lack or insufficiency of manganese in the tissues. This theory is also corroborated by the findings of Lund, Shaw and Drinker (*J. Exp. Med.*, 1921, 33, 231) who could not detect any manganese in guinea-pig tissues. The author has also found that guinea-pig liver is much poorer in manganese content than the liver of the goat and the fowl. These results will be communicated in due course.

In the light of the author's investigations it would now be possible to explain the inability of the primates and the guinea-pig to synthesise their requirements of ascorbic acid within their bodies like other animal species. This inability can be explained, as already indicated, by the absence in the tissues of sufficient manganese which is the co-ferment of the dehydrogenases responsible for the conversion of the precursors into ascorbic acid. The author also advances the hypothesis that under favourable conditions, man would be able to and does synthesise certain amounts of ascorbic acid within the body.

The precursors and the enzymes are there and only the co-enzyme manganese is not present sufficiently to make the enzyme active. Any condition, therefore, which favours the absorption of greater amounts of manganese by the tissues will also help them to synthesise ascorbic acid *in vivo*. Oleson (*Biochem. Z.*, 1934, 269, 329) found that in soils and in water cultures plants assimilate greater amounts of manganese when the reaction is acid. It is probable that an acid reaction in the small intestines will similarly lead to a greater absorption of manganese by the animal tissues and they would then be able to synthesise ascorbic acid.

Among the factors influencing the reaction in the intestines are the

nature of the diet and its acid-base balance. Carbohydrate diets make the intestinal reaction strongly acid and meat diet also gives an acid reaction. The grain food of birds and flesh food of animals and carrion eating birds thus contribute to an acid intestine resulting in manganese absorption with consequent synthesis of ascorbic acid. Robinson (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1935, **108**, 403) has shown that irrespective of the reaction of the solution introduced into the jejunal loop of a dog, the recovered solution had always a pH of about 6.5. Rat intestines were also found to have a reaction of the mean value of about pH 6.5. Redman, Willimot and Wokes (*Biochem. J.*, 1927, **21**, 589) as well as Abrahamson and Miller (*Proc. Soc. Exp. Biol. Med.*, 1925, **22**, 438) could not get any marked variation in the intestinal pH of rat by varying the diet. The rat and the dog have thus a constant and acid intestine which enables them to absorb sufficient manganese resulting in ascorbic acid synthesis by the animals. It is probable that manganese is absorbed in the lower jejunum and upper ileum where the reaction is acid in the rat and the dog and alkaline in the guinea-pig. This explains the ability of the rat and the dog and the inability of the guinea-pig to synthesise ascorbic acid *in vivo*. The same arguments hold in the case of other animal species which synthesise ascorbic acid. In the case of man, the intestinal reaction will be governed by the nature of his diet and its acid-base balance. If and when the reaction in the small gut becomes acid, sufficient manganese will be absorbed resulting in synthesis of certain amounts of ascorbic acid. Harde and Wolff (*Compt. rend. Soc. Biol.*, 1934, **116**, 288) think that the small intestine is the seat of ascorbic acid synthesis (*cf.* Hopkins, *Chem. Ind.*, 1934, **53**, 874). Hopkins and Slater (*Biochem. J.*, 1935, **29**, 2803) think that both the liver and the small intestines are the seats of ascorbic acid synthesis in the rat. The author's view is that in animals in whom ascorbic acid synthesis occurs, most of the synthesis occurs in the region of manganese absorption, that is, in the lower jejunum and upper ileum.

Certain sections of the Indian people with grossly inadequate intake of ascorbic acid (according to generally accepted standards) do not show any signs of scurvy. This can be explained by their "acid" and carbohydrate-rich diet which makes intestinal reaction acid with consequent ascorbic acid synthesis within the body due to sufficient manganese absorption. Wilson and Mitra (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1938, **26**, 131) carried out some diet surveys in which the garden labourers with an intake of only 26 mg. of ascorbic acid, contained in raw vegetables consumed after thorough cooking, showed no signs of vitamin C deficiency. The actual amounts of ascorbic acid consumed could not be more than 10 to

13 mg. An interesting result was obtained by Hawley, Frazer, Button and Stevens (*J. Nutrition*, 1936, 12, 215) by the ingestion of ammonium chloride and sodium bicarbonate respectively to normal healthy persons. They found greater excretion of ascorbic acid in the former case than in the latter. This greater excretion of ascorbic acid in the urine of persons taking ammonium chloride was due, according to the author's theory, to the acidification of the small gut, absorption of more manganese than normally and synthesis of some ascorbic acid by the subjects.

Rietschel (*Klin. Wschr.*, 1938, 17, 1787) points out that most of the German people do not take more than 10 to 15 mg. of ascorbic acid in the winter and in the spring and yet show no signs of scurvy. He postulates that human requirement is small owing to the alternate oxidation and reduction of ascorbic acid in the body. In a further study by Rietschel and Menschig (*Klin. Wschr.*, 1939, 18, 273); the latter lived on a diet of meat and cereals, cooked with alkali, for 100 days and remained well and free from scurvy. Although serum ascorbic acid fell gradually, the urinary output was normal, 1.0 mg. per 100 c.c. towards the end of the investigation. They explain the non-appearance of scurvy symptoms by Rietschel's previous hypothesis of alternate oxidation and reduction of ascorbic acid in the body. A more plausible explanation, according to the theory of ascorbic acid synthesis in man just postulated, would be that there is some synthesis of ascorbic acid by the subject during the test period. Although Stepp and Schroeder (*Klin. Wschr.*, 1939, 18, 484) discount the possible synthesis of ascorbic acid in man because in the test by Rietschel and Menschig, the serum ascorbic acid fell to 0.06 mg. per 100 c.c. at the end, this can be explained by the supposition that the amount synthesised was wholly metabolised and passed into urine and, therefore, could not raise the serum ascorbic acid content. Rudra's hypothesis on the synthesis of ascorbic acid in man is supported by the fact that generally more ascorbic acid is excreted in urine in acid conditions than in alkaline conditions.

The conclusion of Wright (*Lancet*, 1900, ii, 565; 1908, ii, 725) that scurvy goes with acidosis cannot be given serious consideration. Lepper and Zilva (*Biochem. J.*, 1925, 19, 581) have shown that although plasma bicarbonate in scorbutic guinea-pigs is slightly lower than that in normal animals, owing to the absence of Na and K in scorbutic diets, the pH of the plasma of scorbutic guinea-pigs is practically the same as the pH of the normal ones; the former being just a shade higher than the latter which fact clashes with Wright's conclusion but does not disprove the author's hypothesis. The fact that manganese content of human tissues is practically constant throughout life does not clash with

the claim of many investigators (Giroud, Ratsimamanga, Robinowicz, Ruiz and Cesa, *Compt. rend. Soc. Biol.*, 1936, **123**, 1038 ; Rohmer, Sanders and Bezssonoff, *Nature*, 1934, **136**, 142 ; Banerji, *Curr. Sci.*, 1935, **3**, 355) that in the early months of infancy, ascorbic acid synthesis occurs. Sheldon and Ramage (*Biochem. J.*, 1933, **27**, 674) found that considerably more manganese is found in meconium than can be found in the tissues. The excess of manganese is not explained. The gall bladder was richer in manganese than the liver. It is probable, the small intestines of the newborn babe would have been found, if examined, to be richer in manganese than the adult tissue. This would explain the possible synthesis of ascorbic acid in early infancy and during the later stage of foetal life and inability later when most of the manganese stored in the intestines is exhausted. (cf. also Ramage, Sheldon and Sheldon, *Proc., Roy. Soc.*, 1933, **B**, **113**, 30).

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